

VIRUDDHA IN RELATION TO ADULTRATION AND FOOD POISONING

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Food is the most important constituent required for growth, energy, restoration and maintainance of the immune system of our body. Modern way of lifestyle has changed a lot the way we consume our food in addition to its deteriorating quality, owing to the inferior quality of ingredients used in the preparation and adulteration. Adultration is a major problem now a days and is basically done by lowering the quality of food by mixing or by substitution of inferior quality of components. Sometimes toxic substances are also added which may cause poisoning in body on consumption. In Ayurveda it can be correlated with Viruddha ahara, as it may exhibit unwanted effects if consumed for a long period of time and can show effects like food poisoning (gara Visha). Viruddha aggravates the bodily doshas but does not eliminate them out of the body and also deteriorates sharirastha dhatus.

Methodology: Ayurveda and contemporary literatures as books, journals, articles and related websites were reviewed comprehensively regarding food adulteration and Viruddha ahara.

Result and Discussion: On thorough analysis, it is concluded that Adulteration can be correlated with Sampat viruddha and food poisoning with Sanskara, virya and Matra viruddha grossly. Viruddha or adultrated food acts as slow poison vitiating all dhatus, ultimately leading to poisoning and even genetic changes. Food being the basic necessity of life should be pure and free from any type of adultration. With the advancement and researches in treatment modalities of agadanttra branch of ayurveda, the poisoning caused by

food adulteration or viruddha can be treated in correlation with dushivisha or garavisha chikitsa.

KEYWORDS: Viruddha ahara, adulteration, food poisoning, Sampata, virya, Sanskara and Matra viruddha, garavisha, dushivisha.

INTRODUCTION

Ahara (food) is one of the three Upasthambas^[1] (Sub-pillars of the body) according to classical Ayurvedic texts, which sustains the three major Sthambas (Pillars) of the human body. Ahara is regarded as essential for human body, as it provides the basic nutrition responsible for sustainance of the body.^[2] It is actually thought of as Prana (source of life). According to ayurveda, apathya ahara or unwholesome diet, leads to the advent of numerous illnesses, whereas pathya, or wholesome food, improves a person's health and life span.

Modern way of lifestyle has changed a lot the way we consume our food in addition to its deteriorating quality, owing to the inferior quality of ingredients used in the preparation and adulteration. Adulteration is a major problem now a days and is basically done by lowering the quality of food by mixing or by substitution of inferior quality of components. Sometimes toxic substances are also added which may cause poisoning in body on consumption. 28% of food samples were found to be contaminated, according to the Food Safety and Standards Authority in India. To increase profits, adulteration is carried out on every possible commodity. In India, adulteration is typically found in milk, ghee, vegetable oil, masala powders and spices, ice creams, honey, coffee and tea leaves, flour, sweets, juices, fruits and other culinary ingredients.

Currently, food poisoning is also a common issue that typically results in a mild but occasionally fatal sickness. Foods contaminated with pathogenic microorganisms or toxins are the cause of food poisoning. The contemporary way of living commonly causes food allergies and food poisoning due to many meal combinations and flavour enhancers used in cooking. Food poisoning is also discussed in ayurveda. According to Charak, when it comes to wholesome food, both the body and illnesses are byproducts of what we consume, and the unwholesomeness of a meal is what specifically contributes to illness.

It is comparable to Viruddha ahara in Ayurveda since it can cause effects like food poisoning and other unpleasant side effects if ingested repeatedly as gara Visha. Chakrapani claims that

Viruddha Anna is distinctive in that it aggravates Sharirastha Prakruta Doshas but does not eradicate them from the body. As these vitiated Doshas remain in the body, they interact with Sharirastha Dhatus and put them in a diseased state known as vikrit awastha, which causes a variety of ailments.

Gara visha or artificial poisons are mixtures of poisonous or non-poisonous chemicals. It is created intentionally by combining a number of different ingredients to cause a number of different ailments. In today's era, Gara visha can be attributed to have produced in the body by consumption of viruddha ahara, improper eating habits, and adulteration of food.

CONCEPT OF VIRUDDHA

Viruddha literary means contrast or opposition in particular. Charaka has defined Viruddha Aahara as a certain food products or their combinations, which interrupts the metabolism of body tissues, which in turn inhibits the process of formation of tissues.^[3] These substances which aggravate Doshas but does not eliminate them out of the body or again pacify them back to their normal state and also contradicts with the properties of doshas and dhatus.^[4]

These food substances may exhibit unwanted effects if consumed for a long period of time and can also show effects like food poisoning, which can be correlated with Gara Visha.

There are total 18 types of Viruddha Aahara as explained by acharya Charaka and their commentators Chakrapani and Gangadhara. Consumption of Viruddha Aahara leads to numerous diseases by aggravating Sharirastha Prakruta Doshas and deteriorating Prakruta Dhatus. So, one should have proper understanding of all the types of Viruddha Aahara, so as to avoid consumption of incompatible dietary articles by the fast food influenced society and people of today's era.

COMPARISON OF GARA VISHA WITH FOOD POISONING

Gara visha affects persons who have poor habits due to the changed modern lifestyle that result in continuous consumption of adulterated food or incompatible food. The Agada tantras concept of Gara visha has several applications. It is primarily divided into two types, Savisha dravya samayogaja visha, which is a mixture of two or more poisonous chemicals, and Nirvisha dravya samyogaja visha, which is a combination of two non-poisonous substances.

Gara visha, according to Acharya Charaka, causes chronic toxicity and is Kalantara-avipaki (slow absorption and stay indigestible). Food, milk, and beverage additives toxicogenesis is

very similar to that of gara visha, which slows down digestion and absorption in the gastrointestinal tract.

Contrarily, food poisoning is a condition brought on by eating food that has been infected with germs. This is caused by bacteria, viruses, parasites, fungi, toxins or other organisms getting into the body through contaminated food or water. Food poisoning is divided into two categories as Non-Bacterial and Bacterial. Salmonella group of organisms are primarily responsible for food poisoning, since enterotoxins are produced by staphylococcus, while the other type by chlostridium botulinum, which multiplies in food and creates exotoxins, producing botulism.

In Ayurveda the non-bacterial food poisoning may be related to viruddha Aahara or Garavisha, which may be related to food allergies, endogenous toxins, compounded poisons, etc. and cause a number of medical conditions, including loss of appetite, skin conditions, eruptions, Alaska (intestinal obstruction), Vilambika (paralytic ileus), etc. While On the other hand, the bacterial food poisoning may be linked to a krimi infestation. According to acharya Sushruta, one of the cause of Atisar is Krimidosh, which means microorganism affect the human body and cause many infectious diseases.^[5-8]

RELATION OF ADULTRATION WITH SAMPATA VIRUDDHA

If food includes any poisonous components, any important or valuable component has been completely or partially removed, or a less expensive item has been replaced for it, then it is said to be adulterated. If it is coloured by using prohibited colours, if it was produced, packaged, or stored in unhygienic circumstances, if the quality falls short of expectations, if it comes from an infected animal, the food item can be categorised as adulterated. Fever, nausea, diarrhoea, abdominal discomfort, neurological weakness, paralysis, and, if untreated, death are among the common initial symptoms of food adulteration.

It can be loosely associated with sampata viruddha in ayurveda. Consuming things that lack the appropriate qualities, such as those that are not mature or over-mature, refined, or contaminated, is referred to as sampata viruddha, as sampata means richness of quality. Food products manufactured using substances that are harmful or of low quality, or from which the primary active ingredient or chemical constituent has already been taken out, might be compared to sampata viruddha since their quality is diminished by interfering with their natural state.

Additionally, certain non-nutritive food additives are purposefully added to food in small amounts to enhance appearance, flavour, texture, and storage qualities. Some of the harmful chemical additives in our common foods include sodium nitrate, BHA and BHT, which have been linked to a number of malignancies, behavioural issues, heart failure, and renal failure. Due to their extensive use in the farm fields, certain pesticide residues are also observed in our fruits and vegetables.

All of these methods reduce food quality and ultimately lead to sampata viruddha. Since Mahastrotas are responsible for intake, absorption and assimilation, the harmful consequences of contaminated food begins from here and provide the groundwork for a number of ailments.

RELATION OF FOOD POISONING WITH SANSKARA, VIRYA AND MATRA VIRUDDHA

It is previously known that substances considered to be viruddha ahara are those that contain the opposing or contradictory guna of the bodily dhatus and vitiate doshas, generating utkleshta without discharging them from the body and without calming them back to normal. In ayurveda, one of its two type, the non-bacterial food poisoning can be grossly correlated with sanskara, virya and matra viruddha.

The food prepared by wrong method or processing is Sanskara Viruddha.^[9] Example is reheating of food articles such as French Fries or heating of honey or mixing honey with hot substances falls under this category. In ayurveda, it is said that if such food items being consumed will act as viruddha to bodily tissues and will render body prone to different ailments.

While consuming food items having opposite Virya at the same time termed as Virya Viruddha. Example is Ushna Virya fish consumed with Sheeta virya Milk. Now a days fish curries are common which makes use of such kind of combination of ingredients. Being of opposite virya, their combination leads to disturbance of the natural state of dhatus, leading to illnesses.

Lastly there are some food items which act as Viruddha when mixed in equal proportion termed as matra viruddha. Example is Cow's Ghee with Honey in equal proportion.

The consumption of above three viruddhas leads to food poisoning, as by some or other sort

of means, that is either by processing it incorrectly or by consuming foods with opposite potency or by consuming foods which becomes poison on consuming in equal quantity, all these ultimately leads to poisoning in the body and the body to suffer from various diseases.

DISCUSSION

Modern lifestyles has compelled people to consume contaminated or incompatible food and for those who adhere to these lifestyles are more vulnerable to Viruddha Aahara and consumption of adulterated food items. The toxicogenesis of food, milk, and beverage additives is very comparable to that of Virudha Ahara, which lowers Jatharagni (Digestive fire) and absorption in the gastrointestinal system.

Garavisha manifests in a variety of ways, accumulating poisons in human tissues for extended periods of time while still being indigestible. Long-term consequences are brought on by eating processed meals, junk food, and food flavoured, coloured, or preserved with additives. The signs of gara visha can be seen in a variety of health risks brought on by metallic toxins (such as those found in canned food and plastic wrappers), drunkenness, unhealthy eating patterns, etc. showing the denatured and cumulative effects garavisha.

To avoid poisoning, precautions must be taken. The food borne illnesses can be prevented by proper storing, cooking, cleaning and handling of edible foods. One should be avoiding the processed, packed and canned food items and try to take fresh food always in dinner, lunch or breakfast.

The techniques of periodic detoxification should be advocated among those who are more likely to acquire this kind of poisoning. It is best to use pathyapathya and panchakarma treatment and counselling. It's important to inform the general public about unhealthy eating habits and lifestyle choices.

There must be legislation to guarantee that the food sold to customers complies with safety requirements. The most significant body that monitors and controls food safety and standards in India is the FSSAI. Standards for food items are governed by the Food Safety and Standards Act, 2006 (FSSA), 2011 (FSSA).

To ensure the safety of the food item, several practices should be carried out on an individual basis. One of them is to always choose branded products, particularly those that bear the ISI logo. If you have any remaining concerns about its quality, you may complain or let the firm

know. We consumers can stop this problem only if we begin to act. Additionally, try to get fruits and veggies from organic markets. We all have a limited amount of room, but if a few readily grown vegetables on balconies, courtyards, or terraces, it may be very beneficial to us. Try making your own masala powders rather than purchasing pre-made ones. Consumers need to be made aware of the quick tests for spotting food adulteration.

According to Agad tantra, following proper Sanshodhana of the body through Panchkarma procedures, acute or chronic toxicities brought on by food adulteration can be treated with either Dushi visha chikitsa or Gara visha chikitsa (depending on the type of adulterant).

CONCLUSION

After thorough analysis, it has been shown that food poisoning and adulteration may be substantially connected with Sanskara, virya, and Matra viruddha. All dhatus are slowly poisoned by viruddha, or adulterated food, which eventually causes poisoning and even genetic mutations.

Since food is a basic human need, it should be pure and unadulterated in any way. There are numerous things that have a significant impact on health, but none are more effective than the food we consume. Furthermore, eating tainted food opens the door to a host of ailments, making public health knowledge of eating the right foods tampering crucial. Everyone should take precautions to protect their health against tainted food.

With the aforementioned review research, we can draw the conclusion that eating food that has been adulterated has a striking resemblance to the ailments that result from eating Viruddha (incompatible food), which in turn can be related with gara visha. Adulterated foods may contribute to modern lifestyle-related health issues, which are known to be attributed to have resulted because of food poisoning or viruddha aharajanya vishaktata.

To investigate the therapeutic effects of Dushivishari agada and other agadas on these disorders, systematic clinical studies must be conducted. This will allow researchers to determine the agadas' efficacy in treating these conditions and their ability to cure any afflictions, if any.

REFERENCES

1. Agnivesha, Charaka, Drudabala, Chakrapani Datta. In: Acharya YT(Edi.). Charaka Samhita with Ayurveda Deepika Commentary. Reprint Edition. Varanasi: Chaukhamba

- Publications, 2015; 152.
2. Charaka Samhita (Charak Chandrika Hindi commentary). Brahmanand Tripathi, Ganga Sahay Pandey, editors. 1st ed. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Surbharti Prakashan; 2007. Sutra Sthana, 11/35; 239.
 3. Agnivesha. In: Charaka, Dridhabala, Charaka Samhita, Sutra Sthana, 26/81. Reprint. Vaidya Yadavaji Trikamaji Acharya., editor. Varanasi: Chaukhambha publishing house, 2016; 149.
 4. Vagbhata. In: Ashtanga Hridaya Samhita Sutra Sthana, 7/45. Reprint. Vaidya A. M. Kunte, Vd. Harishastri Paradkar editor. Varanasi: ChaukhambhaSamskrita Samsthana, 2011; 137.
 5. Dr. Bramhanand Tripathi, editor 'CharakSamhita' of Agnivesha, Chukhambha Surbharati Prakashan, Varanasi; Sutrasthan, p.no.102-108, Vimansthan, 665-669.
 6. Shastri Ambikadatta, editor 'Sushrutsamhita' vol.I Chukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, Varanasi; klp., 2: 3237.
 7. Ravidatta Tripathi, AshtangaSangraha, Chukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, Delhi.
 8. Text Book of Agadtantra published by Rashtriyam Shikshan Mandal, Pune with grant in aid from Department of Ayush. 1st edition, 2008; 62-64.
 9. Agnivesha. In: Charaka, Dridhabala, Charaka Samhita, Sutra Sthana, 26/86-87. Reprint. Vaidya Yadavaji Trikamaji Acharya., editor. Varanasi: Chaukhambha publishing house, 2016; 150.